

Evaluation of a metaprocess for migrating legacy applications to microservice-based architectures

You are being invited to take part in a scientific study that aims to evaluate ASCE [*fictitious name*]. ASCE intends to serve as a basis for helping organizations and development teams define processes for migrating monolithic applications to a microservice-based architecture. Therefore, ASCE is a process for defining processes, in other words, a metaprocess.

You will contribute to the study by completing this electronic questionnaire. It starts with questions about your profile and your experience with migrating existing applications to microservices. Then, you will be introduced to an overview of ASCE and how it can be used to define migration processes. After reading this description, you will be able to express your opinion ASCE.

It is important to point out that participating in this study is completely voluntary. You are completely free to withdraw from collaborating, without any kind of prejudice or need to justify your decision, by simply closing your Internet browser, even if you have already started completing this questionnaire. As you will not need to provide any information that can identify you, your participation will be anonymous. However, because of this anonymity, withdrawing from the study will not be possible once you have submitted your answers. The answers you provide will be stored and processed by the research team for analysis purposes and used, in whole or in part, in scientific publications. Again, you will not be identified in any material that is produced from this study.

To take part in this study, you must ensure that you have experience developing microservices and express your explicit consent before proceeding to answer this questionnaire. This is a low-risk activity and no disadvantages associated with your participation have been identified. However, if you feel any physical discomfort or tiredness while answering this questionnaire, you can pause the task and resume it whenever you wish. You can also use the physical device (PC, smartphone, tablet) of your choice and answer the questionnaire at your convenience, taking as much time as you like.

If you have any questions about this questionnaire, you can contact one of the researchers responsible for the study [*contact details omitted for double-blind review purposes*].

* Indicates a mandatory question

1. Informed Consent *

After having been informed of the objectives of this study and how the answers I provide to this questionnaire will be treated, I certify that:

1. the objectives of the study have been presented to me;
2. I have read and understood what I will need to do while completing this questionnaire;
3. I have had the opportunity to clarify any doubts about my participation in the study;
4. my participation is entirely voluntary;
5. the answers I provide in this questionnaire are completely anonymous;
6. I am under no obligation to take part in this study and can withdraw from it at any time;
7. the researchers have my consent to use the answers I provide in this questionnaire, in whole or in part, in scientific publications without identifying me.

Choose only one option

- I agree to voluntarily participate in this study.
- I do not agree to take part in this study.

About your profile

2. What is your highest level of education? *

If you are still an undergraduate student, check the "Undergraduate" box. The same applies to all other levels.

Choose only one option.

- Undergraduate
- Specialization
- Master
- PhD
- I do not have a degree in Computing

3. How much professional experience do you have? *

Choose only one option.

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- Between 3 and 5 years
- Between 5 and 10 years
- More than 10 years

4. What is your role at your current workplace? *

5. How do you rate your current level of knowledge and experience in microservices? *

On the process of migrating applications to microservices

6. Have you ever been involved in an application migration process to a microservices-based architecture?

Choose only one option.

- Yes
- No

7. Could you briefly describe how did the migration process(es) go? *

8. How long did the migration process(es) take? *

9. What activities did you carry out during the migration process(es)? *

10. How do you rate the efficiency of the migration process(es)? *

Choose only one option.

1 2 3 4 5

Very | Very efficient

11. What did you use as a basis for defining the activities needed for the migration? *

12. What positive and negative points did you identify in your experience(s) with migration? *

13. Based on the answer to the previous question, what were the implications of these points for the migration?

14. How important do you consider having a well-defined guideline or process to guide migration?

Choose only one option.

- Not important
- Not very important
- Indifferent
- Important
- Very important

15. What problems do you think you have faced or would face in the future in the absence of these guidelines?

ASCE overview

ASCE is the metaprocess for migrating legacy applications to microservices based on the Essence Kernel, an OMG standard providing elements and a visual language for defining, sharing, and reusing Software Engineering methods and practices. ASCE reuses and extends the elements described in Essence to establish a set of practices that further comprise a larger process for migrating to microservices.

Essential elements: Areas of Concern and Alphas

ASCE is divided into three areas of concern, namely *Customer*, *Solution*, and *Endeavor*. Each area of concern has a set of *Alphas*, as shown in Figure 1. *Alphas* describe the essential elements that a development team works with, each with a set of states indicating the state of progress of the work. *Customer*, represented in green, defines the alphas related to those responsible for devising and executing the migration and the motivations for carrying it out. *Solution*, represented in yellow, brings together the changes needed to carry out the migration and the microservices (*Services*) created from the required changes. Finally, *Endeavor*, represented in blue, refers to team management, working methods, and the elements that support the work.

Figure 1 - M3K Alphas

ASCE abstraction

Figure 2 shows an abstraction of the ASCE for developing the migration process to microservices. To facilitate understanding, the ASCE has been simplified into five phases.

Phase 1 begins with stakeholders and software architects investigating the legacy application and proposing improvements to the application that can be achieved by using microservices, such as scalability, flexibility, and maintainability. This investigation moves on to Phase 2, in which the opportunities are elaborated as changes to the application to be migrated, as well as defining how the migration process will be carried out, migrating the entire application at once or incrementally

After defining the changes to be made, Phase 3 ensures that the development environment is ready to be used and tasks are distributed among the team, thus allowing the migration to occur smoothly. Phase 4 presents the development of the microservices in the designated environments based on the changes identified by the stakeholders and software architects. This stage also concerns testing the functionalities and carrying out necessary validations of the developed artifacts.

In an incremental migration, it is possible to move on to migrating another feature at the end of Phase 4. When a feature has been tested or the entire application has been migrated and is ready for customers to use, the microservice-based application moves on to Phase 5, which makes it available for access beyond the development team.

Figure 2 - Definition of a migration process using ASCE

Activities and skills involved in migration

ASCE aims to help companies and developers define processes by analyzing common aspects and making it easier not only to propose tasks but also to monitor these activities. ASCE uses the definition of *Activity Spaces*, which are generic tasks for which the team responsible for the migration can propose specific tasks for their domains. As shown in Figure 3, *Customer* defines the Activity Spaces related to analyzing the opportunity for migration and the application and validating the migration results. In *Solution*, designing, refactoring/creating, integrating, and testing the developed microservices are carried out. *Endeavor* defines the tasks for monitoring, environment definition, and delivery of solutions. The process is designed with this set of tasks in mind, which are common to migration processes from legacy applications to microservices in the literature.

Figure 3 - Activity Spaces

Competencies

Figure 4 shows the skills needed to define a migration process. In *Customer*, it is necessary to understand the domain to which the application will be migrated. In *Solution*, the competencies responsible for the entire technical stage are defined, defining the changes and designing and finalizing the microservices. Finally, *Endeavor* requires the skills of planning and organizing tasks

Figure 4 - ASCE Competencies

Each task requires a set of skills, ranging from knowledge of a particular technology to team management. Figure 5 shows an example of the activities and skills used during the execution of Phase 2 for Phase 3, which is represented in Figure 2.

Figure 5 - Extent of activities performed and skills required

Figure 6 shows an overview of the execution of the phases shown in Figure 2, where the process starts at Phase 1 and continues in order until Phase 5. Phase 5 is responsible not only for signifying the end of the migration process but also for enabling new functionalities to be migrated.

Each agent has a well-distributed role in ASCE, thus allowing all the actors to work together to achieve the final objectives of the migration. Monitoring all the phases by the team responsible for managing the migration is simplified by the fact that each possible new microservice will be implemented in a specific phase, thus making it possible to progress and control the migrations carried out.

Figure 6 - Migration phases

ASCE Application Example

ASCE defines the *Alphas*, *Activity Spaces*, and *Competencies* for developing a migration process from monolithic architectures to microservices. Alphas and Competencies are standardized for all tasks, representing the primary agents and artifacts in the development process and the capabilities needed for the migration.

The activities in the migration process are detailed in the Activity Spaces, as shown in Figure 7. These activities are specific to the application domain, so migration must follow a sequence of steps, which will be exemplified in the following figures.

Figure 7 - Activities obtained from Activity Spaces

Based on the analysis of the activities required for the migration and the *Alphas* that represent the main points of the ASCE, the competencies needed for this migration are defined, as shown in Figure 8. The first competence is understanding the company's domain and the application to be migrated. For developing microservices, in *Solution*, there is a need to understand what microservices are and how they are implemented, how to design an application, and how to refactor, implement, and test it. Finally, in *Endeavor*, the migration actors must be committed and know how to manage to deliver the desired artifacts.

Figure 8 - Migration *Competencies*

Example of using ASCE

Once the tasks have been defined, it is possible to structure sequences of actions that correspond to the migration process that will be applied. The first stage of the process, shown in Figure 9, represents the study of the application to be migrated to microservices. In this example, the architectural team meets with the development team to describe the microservices architecture, detailing how it is developed and deployed. This understanding is essential to achieving competence in instruction in developing microservices.

This stage is necessary if the development team is unfamiliar with the architecture. Otherwise, the migration can move on to the next stage described in Figure 10 below.

Figure 9 - Application Study

Definition of the changes to be made

After understanding what a microservices architecture is and how to develop it, the stakeholders need to analyze the opportunities that can be achieved by migrating from a legacy architecture to one based on microservices.

Stakeholders need to understand the application that will be migrated so that any questions about how it works can be answered. This understanding results in an analysis of the application that generates the motivations needed to carry out the migration. These motivations generate the changes necessary to create microservices.

Figure 10 - Analyzing opportunities

Definition of microservices

Once the reasons for the migration have been defined, the architectural team must analyze which changes are necessary to achieve the objectives set out in the analysis. To do this, the architectural team must be able to carry out an architectural redesign of the original application and lead the migration, assigning tasks, and organizing the changes.

The architectural changes are then defined by the architectural team, representing the microservice design that will be developed based on the motivations. Then, based on the changes made, the microservice is created, which requires architectural development skills.

At the end of this process, in addition to the microservice that needs to be created, the microservice documentation is presented to help with the changes to be made by the development team.

team in the subsequent stages. Figure 11 shows the changes that will be made to define the microservices.

Figure 11 - Definition of microservices

Preparing for the development stage

Figure 12 shows the process required to start work. The activity of preparing the environment ensures that developers have all the necessary configurations for this task before they start developing.

To make the environment available, it is necessary to define and make the microservices environment available, thus requiring management skills. This makes it possible to integrate and test the microservices during and after development.

Figure 12 - Preparing for development

Development of microservices

Figure 13 shows the actual development of the microservices. Note that the decision to migrate the functionalities at once or to carry out an incremental migration is a project decision, which should have been foreseen during the discussions of changes to the architecture, shown Figure 11.

The development team receives the tasks and group divisions for the development of the microservice, which requires management competency to deliver the artifacts to be produced. The services are then implemented through the work of implementing and refactoring the original application by the developers, who need refactoring skills. Finally, the microservices are implemented.

Figure 13 - Development of the microservice(s)

Final stages of the process

Once the microservices have been developed and the tests have been carried out to guarantee the correctness of the new version of the application, it is necessary to validate the work carried out as shown in Figure 13.

Once the developers have delivered the application, it's time to finalize the work, so that the artifact developed is deployed for access by clients, thus generating the microservice. This microservice is used by the stakeholders, who then validate that the intended objectives have been achieved and the system is working as intended, requiring an understanding of the business.

Figure 14 - Validation and completion of the work carried out

Different approaches

Developing a migration process can follow different approaches to those presented here, with the example here serving as a guide to applying the ASCE in defining a process.

Decisions on activities depend exclusively on the number of people taking part in the migration and the context of the application, in which the ASCE serves as a basis for helping develop these possible solutions.

ASCE evaluation

16. How important do you consider the definition of roles as proposed by ASCE?

** Choose only one option.*

- Not important
- Not very important
- Indifferent
- Important
- Very important

17. Do you believe the tasks proposed by the ASCE *Activity Spaces* are essential in migrating from monolithic architectures to microservices? If not, why?

18. How important do you consider the existence of competencies for developing activities during the migration process?

Choose only one option.

- Not important
- Not very important
- Indifferent
- Important
- Very important

19. How useful do you consider ASCE in migrating applications to microservices?

** Choose only one option.*

- Not useful
- Not very useful
- Indifferent
- Useful
- Very useful

20. How likely would you use ASCE in your development team to migrate applications to microservices?

Choose only one option.

1 2 3 4 5

Unlil Very likely

21. How do you assess the impact of using ASCE in a migration process?

** Choose only one option.*

- Very negative impact: ASCE can cause several problems during migration.
- Some negative impact: ASCE can cause some problems during migration.
- No impact: ASCE will make no difference to the migration process.
- Some positive impact: ASCE can help with some stages of the migration process.
- Very positive impact: ASCE can help at all stages of the migration.

22. Do you agree with the following statement? *

ASCE helps migrate legacy applications to an architecture based on microservices.

Choose only one option.

- 1 - Strongly disagree
- 2 - Disagree
- 3 - Neutral
- 4 - Agree
- 5 - Totally agree

23. Overall, what are the positive and negative points of the ASCE?

24. If you think the ASCE is insufficient, limited, or misses any step, what could be added to it?

25. Would you like to add any comments?
